

INSULATING SANDWICH FAÇADE SYSTEM WITH TEXTILE REINFORCED CEMENT (TRC) COMPOSITES: STRUCTURAL CASE DESIGN AND LARGE-SCALE TESTING

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ABSTRACT

Insulating sandwich panels with textile reinforced cement (TRC) composite faces can be lightweight and prefabricated with the dimensions of one full storey. Hence, they can facilitate the construction or (thermal) renovation process. This paper investigates their structural feasibility by means of large-scale mechanical testing and case study design. The mechanical response of the panels was simulated by a finite element model in Abaqus under different loads as prescribed by European standards. Bending tests on 2.2 m span sandwich plates validated the model predictions and confirmed the structural feasibility of TRC sandwich panels as large-span, self-bearing façade cladding.

KEYWORDS

Textile reinforced concrete (TRC); sandwich panel; self-bearing plate; façade cladding; large-span bending test; loadbearing capacity; finite element model; design

INTRODUCTION

As governmental regulations increase the energetic and thermal demands for buildings, the market for insulating building solutions increases. Particularly renovation of existing dwellings and buildings is challenging. Large, prefabricated sandwich panels with cement composite faces offer great possibilities in this context. Using textile instead of steel reinforcement, the sandwich faces can be manufactured very thin. The resulting sandwich panels are lightweight, even when prefabricated with the dimensions of one full storey. As such, they can facilitate the installation process. The installation time on site can be reduced to a minimum to limit the nuisance for the residents.

In literature, sandwich panels with TRC faces were widely experimentally characterised ((Junes, 2016), (Vervloet, 2018), (Colombo, 2015), (Nguyen, 2015), (Hegger, 2010), (Shams, 2014)) and numerically modelled ((Williams Portal, 2017), (Djamai, 2017)). To assess their structural feasibility for large-span cladding, however, full-scale plate tests were performed in the present study, as well as a case study. The panels consist of a thermal insulation core of 200 mm thickness in EPS, onto which a TRC face of 5 mm thickness – reinforced by glass fibre textiles - is laminated. In view of the application as discretely connected façade panels, the sandwich plates were tested in bending. Three identical plates were tested, and monitored with Digital Image Correlation to obtain a full-field image of the surface displacements and strains. The mechanical response of the panels was simulated by a finite element model in Abaqus. Comparison of simulations and experiments not only validates the numerical model, but gives also valuable insights in the possible failure modes of the sandwich panel. Using the validated numerical model, a case study was designed, applying the self-bearing panels as façade elements for a multiple storey building. Both the ultimate limit state and serviceability limit state, as prescribed by European standards, were evaluated considering the different load cases relevant for the application: selfweight, wind and thermal action (thermal gradient between inside and outside of the panel). The case study answers the research question of what occurring stress states, panel deformations and critical points can be expected in a typical sandwich panel application.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This paragraph describes the materials used and the manufacturing of the sandwich panels, their geometry and test setup, as well as the measurement equipment used for monitoring.

Materials

A commercially available mortar (Tillman B.V., 2019) was chosen as cementitious matrix. This Portland cement-based mix includes a series of polymers to obtain a shrinkage-compensated mortar. As it is often used for gluing insulation boards on existing walls, a good adhesion with insulation materials is assured. The maximum grain size equals 0,5 mm. For preparation of the mortar, a water to binder mass ratio of 0,15 was considered. The main mechanical characteristics were determined by performing six flexural and twelve compression tests following the European Standards (EN 196-1:2016) (Belgian Bureau for Standardisation, 2016). The flexural strength $f_{ct,f}$ equalled 6.35 +- 0.45 MPa and the compressive strength f_{cc} was equal to 23.17 +- 1.59 MPa.

The cementitious matrix is reinforced with a commercially available technical textile (Knauf, 2019). The AR glass rovings are covered with a styrene-butadiene coating and woven in an orthogonal mesh with a mesh size of 5 mm in both directions (Figure 1a). The total surface weight equals 200 g/m², the weight of the fibres (without coating) 165 g/m². The textile has a nominal tensile strength of 2500 N per 50 mm (Knauf, 2019).

Expanded polystyrene (EPS, density 269 kg/m³) was used to materialise the insulating core of the sandwich structures. The properties of the used EPS were determined following ASTM C165-95 (American Society for Testing and Materials, 2011). Out of six compressive tests on EPS cubes with nominal dimensions of 200 mm x 200 mm x 200 mm, the average E-modulus was calculated to be 9.6 +-0.4 MPa. An identical E-modulus was observed in all directions.

Figure 1: Manufacturing of sandwich plate specimens

Specimen dimensions and manufacturing

Three sandwich plates of 2500 mm by 2500 mm, 210 mm thickness were fabricated. A hand lay-up technique was used to apply a 5 mm thickness TRC layer, reinforced with one textile grid, at both sides of the EPS core with a thickness of 200 mm. The mortar was cast in two times and in between the textile grid was impregnated in the mortar (Figure 1b). The fibre volume fraction of the TRC faces was equal to 0.65% in the loading direction. To prevent premature evaporation, the faces were sealed with a plastic cover. All plates were stored for at least 28 days at ambient temperature (approximately 20°C) and a relative humidity between 45% and 60%.

Test setup

Placed on discrete, point-wise supports near the corners, the plates were uniformly loaded by placing weight bags (Figure 2). The weight was added in discrete loading steps of 0.5 kN/m^2 . To avoid local stress concentrations, square distribution plates of 200 mm by 200 mm were placed at the supports. At five locations, the deflection was measured using analogue calibres: one in the middle of the plate, and four near the corners to verify if the plate deformed equally. One quarter of the plate was monitored with Digital Image Correlation to map cracking patterns. The displacement and cracking patterns were captured up to 5.0 kN/m^2 . To avoid possible damage to the measuring devices, they were removed for further loading steps.

a) Side view

b) Top view

c) Uniformly loaded with weight bags

d) Support under plate corner

Figure 2: Test set-up of sandwich plate under uniformly distributed loading

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

Model definition

A finite element model (FEM) was established in the finite elements software Abaqus 6.14 (Standard/Explicit model). The EPS core was modelled as a homogenous solid, discretised using eight-node linear brick elements (C3D8R). For the TRC faces, the shell theory could be applied since their thickness was small compared to the other dimensions. Meshing of the faces was done using four-node quadrilateral shell elements, including finite membrane strains (S4R). The Simpson integration rule was used for five integration points over the thickness. A perfect bond was assumed between the faces and the core. In order to simulate the assumed perfect bond, a tie constraint was implemented.

Material modelling

Different constitutive laws exist for the implementation of the insulating foam; linear elastic behaviour (Cuypers 2011), (Williams Portal 2017) and crushable foam (Colombo 2018), (Djamai 2017), (Vervloet 2019) showed good results in previous research. Implementing linear elastic material behaviour is computationally less expensive. Also, no deformation of the core is observed during the experimental campaign which justifies this choice. Therefore the EPS-core was implemented as a linear elastic material with an E-modulus of 9.6 MPa and a Poisson's ratio of 0.12.

TRC was modelled by superimposing a linear elastic behaviour with the inbuilt Concrete Damaged Plasticity Model (CDP). Tysmans (Tysmans, 2015) demonstrated that among all nonlinear concrete models available in Abaqus, the CDP delivers the most accurate prediction of the actual material behaviour. Within the CDP model, the degradation of the isotropic elasticity is induced by tensile and compressive plastic strains. The main principle of the model is based on a yield surface, introduced as a modified Drucker-Prager function. The effective stress and plastic strain variables define the elastoplastic response with two possible failure modes; tensile cracking and compressive-crushing. The parameters to define the yield surface were taken equal to the values of concrete and are in correspondence with (Tysmans, 2010). The compressive behaviour is inserted as linear elastic with an E-modulus of 28.3 GPa up to the compressive strength of 23.2 MPa.

The tensile material behaviour of TRC was based on experimental data. Nine uniaxial tensile tests (Figure 3) were performed on prismatic specimens with nominal dimensions of 500 mm x 75 mm x 10 mm on an Instron universal electromechanical test bench 5885. The specimens thus had double the thickness of the TRC faces of the sandwich panels; therefore two instead of one textile layers were introduced to achieve the same fibre volume fraction. The tests were displacement controlled at a rate of 1 mm/min. Strains were measured with DIC, averaged over a length of 320 mm. Two different failure modes were observed: tensile rupture of the fibrous reinforcement or fibre pullout in the clamps.

Figure 3: Stress-strain behaviour of TRC faces of sandwich panels, experimental (tensile) results and averaged behaviour as implemented in the material model

Out of the nine obtained tensile stress-strain curves, one average reference behaviour was determined (Figure 3). The stresses of each specimen were interpolated on an equal strain axis. Per strain level the average stress was calculated. The typical non-linear tensile behaviour of TRC was distinguished. The first linear stage of this average reference curve was characterised by a stiffness of 13.5 GPa. The linear elastic behaviour was completed with the CDP model to account for the plastic behaviour. This plastic behaviour was defined by inputting the plastic strains and true stresses. At a stress of 1.35 MPa, the tensile behaviour becomes non-linear.

Model geometry, boundary conditions and loading

To optimise computational time, only quarter of the plate was modelled by defining two symmetry planes XY and YZ (Figure 4a). This assumption is valid since the geometry and boundary and loading conditions are symmetric around these planes. A convergence study showed that 20 mm was an adequate mesh size.

To match the experimental conditions, the supports were introduced as rectangular plate-shaped rigid bodies (infinitely stiff), translationally restricted in all directions and rotationally restricted around the Y-axis. The interaction between these rigid bodies and the sandwich plate was modelled as a default hard contact normal behaviour and a frictionless tangential behaviour. The self-weight of the plate itself was relatively small and thus neglected. The load was introduced as a uniform pressure load, applied on the area between the supports (Figure 4b).

b) Side view of meshed plate model under uniformly distributed load
Figure 4: Numerical model of sandwich plates

LOADBEARING CAPACITY OF SANDWICH PLATES: EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND COMPARISON TO NUMERICAL MODEL

Since the experiments were monitored up to 5.0 kN/m², only a limited part of the load-displacement curves was captured. The initial linear stage and the beginning of the post-cracking stage were captured by all calibres. The measured stiffness of this last branch is used to extrapolate the curves up to the ultimate failure load. As shown in Figure 5, all three plates show a similar behaviour. A good agreement is observed between the experimental and numerical results, as well as for the

displacement measured and predicted near the corner (Figure 5b) as for the displacement in the centre of the plate (Figure 5a).

On the numerical load-displacement curve of the centre point also some specific points are indicated, which correspond to different levels of maximum tensile stress attained in the lower TRC face (as similarly indicated on the stress-strain curve). Up to point A, the numerical model follows the experimental curves closely and the initial stiffness is predicted very accurately. The first cracking load is captured accurately as well (point A). Differences between the numerical response and the experimental results arise after this point. All plates show an abrupt loss in stiffness, while the numerical prediction has a more gradual loss of stiffness following the material input of TRC. It should also be mentioned that this material behaviour is inserted as an isotropic behaviour. For uncracked TRC, this assumption is valid since the stiffness of the matrix is dominant and identical in all directions. Once a crack is formed, an orthotropic material behaviour is more likely. The efficiency of the fibres, and thus their alignment with respect to the loading direction is the determining factor. However, the impact of assuming isotropic material behaviour instead of the actual orthotropic behaviour remains limited as confirmed later by comparison of the DIC measurements with the numerical output.

a) displacement measured at the centre of the plate

b) displacement measured near the corner of the plate

Figure 5: comparison of the load-displacement behaviour predicted by the numerical mode versus observed on the three performed bending tests

In the numerical model, the failure mode corresponding to reaching the ultimate tensile stress is indicated with point C. The experimental failure load is well below this load level, namely around 9.6 kN/m² for all plates (point B). Indeed none of the plates achieved failure by tensile resistance, but each of them failed in shear, near one of the supports (Figure 7a). At the experimentally observed

failure load of 9.6 kN/m^2 , the maximum tensile stress in the lower face is (only) 4.4 MPa (point B). The numerical stress maps (Figure 6) are therefore investigated further at the experimentally observed failure load of 9.6 kN/m^2 . As can be seen in Figure 6a, the maximum tensile stress in the lower face (4.4 MPa) is not attained in the middle of the plate but rather near the free edges. The same is observed for the compressive stress in the upper face, a minimum of -10.4 MPa is attained near the free edge (Figure 6b). In these zones the appearing moment is largest, which explains the larger stresses. At a load of 9.6 kN/m^2 , a maximum shear stress of 145 kPa is numerically attained near one of the supports (Figure 6c), which exceeds the maximum allowed shear stress of 125 kPa of the used EPS. At point D (8.2 kN/m^2) on Figure 5, this maximum allowed shear stress is numerically attained. The numerical model is thus somewhat more conservative in the prediction of the failure stress. Note that no actual failure criteria are included in the model, so it is up to the designer to verify the stress states and check all possible failure modes at a given load level.

Figure 6: FEM output at failure (9.6 kN/m^2): (a) tensile stress, (b) compressive stress and (c) shear stress.

An extra validation of the numerical model is done by using the DIC output, namely by mapping the cracking patterns. Generally, cracks are formed orthogonally to the principal tensile stresses. As shown in Figure 7b, the principal tensile stress vectors calculated by FEM (indicated by the red arrows) evolve diagonally in the region of the supports and orthogonally towards the middle of the plate. This prediction is confirmed by the observed cracking patterns, most cracks are found to be perpendicular to principal stress vectors.

Figure 7: (a) Shear failure of the sandwich plate near the corners, (b) the principal stress vectors obtained via Abaqus conform the observed cracking behaviour, mapped using DIC.

DESIGN CASE STUDY

Case study description

To evaluate the feasibility of the proposed façade system, a case study of a high-rise building (17 floors and a total height of 52 m) was designed. The elevated height results in significant wind loads which challenge the loadbearing capacity of the façade panels. The previously validated finite element model was used to calculate the effect of the wind and other acting loading conditions. Focus is put on one specific façade panel, of which the geometry and dimensions are shown in Figure 8. The sandwich lay-up is equal to the tested plates: a 200 mm thickness EPS core is cladded at both sides with a 5 mm thickness TRC layer (fibre volume fraction equals 0.65% along the directions of the orthogonal grid). A finishing brick layer of 30 mm thickness is applied at the outer face.

The panel is attached to the bearing structure by means of pointwise anchors. The three upper anchors carry the weight of the panels and restrict the movement in the horizontal direction and the direction normal to the façade plane. The three lower anchors only restrict the movement in the direction normal to the façade plane.

Figure 8: Geometry of the case study, with indication of dimensions (left) and modelled symmetry and boundary conditions (right)

Load cases

During their lifetime, sandwich façade panels will be subjected to different kind of loading conditions. The load cases to be considered for this application are the self-weight of the panels and their finishing layer, the wind load and the temperature gradient due to climatic effects. The different load combinations to account for are prescribed in Eurocode 1 (European Committee for Standardisation, 2002) and specified for sandwich panels in the “European recommendations for sandwich panels” (CIB 1782) (ECCS, 2000).

Besides the self-weight of the sandwich panel (0.22 kN/m^2 , EPS core and TRC faces), also the finishing layer needs to be considered. A brick layer of 30 mm thickness is assumed, equal to a surface load of 0.25 kN/m^2 .

Eurocode 1 prescribes the wind load acting on the walls of a structure, depending on building height, location, etc. According to Eurocode 1, a structure is divided in different zones on which a specified wind load is acting. Based on these calculations, two worst-case scenarios are derived: either a wind suction load of -1.95 kN/m^2 or a wind pressure load of 1.79 kN/m^2 .

When the façade panels are subjected to different climatic conditions, temperature gradients arise from the difference between the outside temperature and the inside temperature. Values for these temperatures are adopted from CIB1782 (ECCS 2000). For the outside face, a minimum temperature in winter of -20°C is proposed for regions in Central Europe. In summer, the temperature at the outside face depends on the colour and the reflectivity of the finishing layer of the façade panel, differing from $+55^\circ\text{C}$ for very light colours to $+80^\circ\text{C}$ for dark colours. The worst-case scenario of $+80^\circ\text{C}$ is assumed for this case-study. For the inside temperature, $+20^\circ\text{C}$ is used in winter and $+25^\circ\text{C}$ in summer.

Model geometry, boundary conditions and loading

For the numerical modelling of the panel, one symmetry plane YZ is defined to reduce the computational time (see Figure 8b). A mesh size of 50 mm is chosen, this is slightly enlarged compared to the previous sections due to the size of the façade panel. The anchors are not simulated in detail since this is out of the interest of this case study. The boundary conditions are smeared over an area of 150 mm by 150 mm, the area of the actual anchorage. For the supports in the upper region of the panels, the displacements are restricted in all directions. At the lower side of the panel only the displacements in the direction normal to the façade plane is set to zero.

The self-weight of the panels is incorporated in the numerical model by defining their density and the direction of the gravity. The finishing layer is implemented as a surface traction acting along the vector (0,-1,0). The wind load is inserted as a surface pressure on the outer face. To account for the temperature differences, predefined fields are defined at the inside and at the outside. A thermal expansion coefficient of 14.5×10^{-6} m/(mK) (International Federation for Structural Concrete 2012) and 70×10^{-6} m/(mK) (Kemisol 2004) is assumed for respectively TRC and EPS.

CASE STUDY: LIMIT STATES VERIFICATION

According to the Eurocode's limit states principle (European Committee for Standardisation 2002), the sandwich panel design is verified under different ultimate limit states (ULS) and serviceability limit states (SLS).

Ultimate limit state

For the ultimate limit state verification (failure verification), four different load combinations are considered (see Table 1). The ULS load combinations include a safety factor of 1.35 on the selfweight (as permanent load) and a safety factor of 1.5 on the wind and thermal loads as variable loads. On the non-dominant variable load a combination coefficient of 0.6 is applied to account for the low probability that all maxima of variable actions occur simultaneously.

Table 1: ULS load combinations

Load combination	Wind		Temperature		Dominant variable action Q_1
	c_p	w	T_{inside}	$T_{outside}$	
	-	kN/m ²	°C	°C	
1	-1.4	-1.95	25	80	Wind
2	1.3	1.79	20	-20	Wind
3	-1.4	-1.95	25	80	Temperature
4	1.3	1.79	20	-20	Temperature

The most probable failure mechanisms in the considered TRC façade panels are related to the maximum tensile and compressive stress of the faces and the shear stress of the core. The maximum values are reported for each ULS load combination in Table 2. Contrarily to the performed experiments, the maximum attained shear stress is found to be considerably small compared to the limit value of 125 kPa for all studied load combinations. For determining the maximum occurring compressive and tensile stresses, the areas of the supports are disregarded such that the design is not based on stress concentrations.

Table 2: Simulation results under ULS load combinations

Load combination	Maximum tensile stress	Maximum compressive stress	Maximum shear stress
	MPa	MPa	kPa
1	2.9	-4.6	12.1
2	2.8	-4.1	9.5
3	3.1	-6.2	10.1
4	3.0	-4.3	8.7

The maximum tensile and compressive stresses are attained for load combination 3. The maximum tensile stress of 3.1 MPa is attained at the inner face near the centre of the panel. Compared to the experimentally determined ultimate stress of TRC of 7.5 MPa, a safety factor of 2.4 exists. Also, the compressive maximum attained stress of -6.2 MPa is much lower than the experimentally determined ultimate compressive stress of -23.2 MPa. A safe design is thus achieved, both for the tensile, compressive and shear stresses.

Serviceability limit state

To evaluate the displacements of sandwich panels, the “European recommendations for sandwich panels” (ECCS, 2000) prescribe to use the SLS frequent load combinations. The different worst-case frequent load combinations are listed in Table 3. The safety factor in SLS equals 1 in all cases. When wind is the dominant variable load, a combination coefficient of 0.75 is applied. In load combination 3 and 4, however, the wind load is the only variable load considered. In these combinations a combination factor equal to 1 needs to be applied.

Table 3: SLS load combinations

Load combination	Wind		Temperature		Dominant variable action Q_1
	c_p	w	T_{inside}	$T_{outside}$	
	-	kN/m ²	°C	°C	
5	-1.4	-1.95	25	80	Wind
6	1.3	1.79	20	-20	Wind
7	-1.4	-1.95	/	/	Wind
8	1.3	1.79	/	/	Wind
9	-1.4	-1.95	25	80	Temperature
10	1.3	1.79	20	-20	Temperature

For combinations 1, 3 and 5 an outwards displacement is observed; combinations 2, 4 and 6 caused an inward displacement. Under the frequent load combinations, the maximum displacement of the panels may not exceed 1/200th of the span. With a span of maximum 2500 mm in our case, the maximum allowed displacement equals 12.5 mm. This requirement is fulfilled for all frequent load combinations (Table 4). The largest total displacement (8.1 mm) is observed for combination 5, occurring near the middle region of the panel (Figure 8).

Table 4: Maximum displacement simulation results under SLS load combinations

Load combination	Maximum displacement
	(mm)
5	7.6
6	6.4
7	5.6
8	5.1
9	8.1
10	6.6

CONCLUSIONS

To stimulate the use of sandwich façade panels with TRC faces, their structural feasibility needs to be confirmed. To do so, a finite element model was established in the commercial software Abaqus to account for different loading conditions. The different assumptions and numerical implementation were validated by uniformly loaded plate experiments. A good agreement was observed between the numerical prediction and experimental outcome. The stiffness measured in the plate experiments matched the numerically predicted stiffness reasonably well. All tested plates showed shear failure near one of the supports. This failure mode was numerically confirmed; the shear stress maps reveal that the maximum core shear stress was exceeded at the experimentally observed failure load.

Figure 8: Displacement field for SLS load combination 5.

The validated numerical implementation was adopted and used to investigate the case study of a façade panel for a high-rise building. When applied as façade system, the sandwich panels are subjected to different loading conditions: self-weight, wind, varying climatic conditions, etc. Different load cases and combinations were therefore defined, both for serviceability and ultimate limit states. Globally, the requirements for all limit states were fulfilled. The maximum attained stresses in ULS were limited compared to the maximum allowed stresses. On the tensile stress a safety factor of 2.4 was observed. For SLS, the maximum observed displacement of 8.1 mm did not exceed the limit of 1/200th of the span (12.5 mm). This conceptual feasibility study thus demonstrated the structural potential of insulation TRC sandwich panels as selfbearing lightweight façade system.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.